

Thermodynamic Functions of *trans*-Acrylyl Chloride

RAJMUHON N. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, Manipur University, Canchipur, Imphal-795 003

Manuscript received 29 July 1991, revised 24 March 1992, accepted 1 April 1992

Statistical determination of thermodynamic properties depends upon the complete knowledge of vibrational frequencies and other molecular spectroscopic data. Direct measurements of these quantities are not usually possible.

In the present work, barriers to internal rotation about the =C—C= single bond and twisting about the C=C double bond have been calculated for *trans*-acrylyl chloride ($\text{CH}_2=\text{CHCOCl}$) from the knowledge of molecular geometry and the observed torsional frequencies from literature¹⁻⁴. Although the vibrational analysis of this molecule has been studied, the thermodynamic functions of this molecule are not reported. The present study was undertaken with a view to compute the thermodynamic functions, namely, heat capacity (C_p°), enthalpy function $(H^\circ - E_0^\circ)/T$, free energy function $(G^\circ - E_0^\circ)/T$ and entropy (S°) for this molecule at a pressure of 1 atm in the temperature range 100–1500 K under the rigid rotor-harmonic oscillator approximation and using the fundamental frequencies available in the literature⁴.

Method: According to Born-Oppenheimer⁵ approximation, the total energy of a system is given by

$$E = E_{\text{trans}} + E_{\text{rot}} + E_{\text{vib}} + E_{\text{elec}} \quad (1)$$

The total partition function Q in terms of energy is given by

$$Q = g_i \exp(-E_i/kT) = Q_{\text{trans}} \cdot Q_{\text{rot}} \cdot Q_{\text{vib}} \cdot Q_{\text{elec}} \quad (2)$$

where g_i is the statistical weight of the i -th energy level, k the Boltzmann constant and T the absolute temperature. The partition function for each type of energy may be evaluated separately from equation

(2) and then the corresponding thermodynamic functions are calculated. The contribution to the thermodynamic functions from different types of partition functions are then added to get the total value. The electronic contribution is small and ignored because E_{elec} is large as compared to kT at ordinary temperatures. The standard expressions⁶ are used in computation for various partition functions and their contribution to different thermodynamic parameters. In the present work, computations of the thermodynamic quantities were made on a IBM-PC computer.

Results and Discussion

The atomic masses and other structural parameters were taken from literature^{4,7} and used as such in the calculations. In computing the principal moments of inertia I_x , I_y and I_z , the molecule has been considered planar (x - y plane) with C_s symmetry and overall symmetry of the molecule has been taken as 1. The computed values of the moment of inertia of the molecule are I_x , $15.87 \times 10^4 \text{ kg m}^2$; I_y , $28.00 \times 10^4 \text{ kg m}^2$ and I_z , $43.8 \times 10^4 \text{ kg m}^2$. *Trans*-acrylyl chloride molecule has two rotational tops, one due to rotation of CH_2 top along C=C double bond and the other due to rotation of COCl top along =C—C= single bond. Here if the barrier height (V^*) is very large, the corresponding rotational frequency can be treated like any other vibrational frequency. Twisting about the double bond, as in the present case, falls on this category and hence C=C torsion of *trans*-acrylyl chloride has been taken as simple fundamental frequency in the calculation. The potential function hindering

internal rotation around the $=C-C=$ single bond in conjugated molecules has been discussed⁸. The barrier height (V^*) due to rotation of $COCl$ top along $=C-C=$ single bond have been calculated as $81.99 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. This value is comparable to that of acrolein⁹ (CHO top along $=C-C=$), and methyl vinylketone⁹ ($C(CH_3)O$ top along $=C-C=$) having V^* 76.15 and 98.0 kJ mol^{-1} respectively. Because of intermediate values of V^* , the hindering internal rotation around the $=C-C=$ single bond for *trans*-acrylyl chloride has been considered and the correc-

tions to various thermodynamic functions are applied with the help of Pitzer and Gwinn's Tables¹⁰. Full programme in Fortran IV has been made and used on IBM-PC computer for the calculation of ir (reduced moment of inertia), F (internal rotational constant) and V^* (barrier height) as well as the thermodynamic functions.

The computed values of the various thermodynamic functions, viz. $(H^\circ - E_0^\circ)/T$, $-(G^\circ - E_0^\circ)/T$, C_p° and S° for *trans*-acrylyl chloride are represented by curves in Fig. 1 at various temperatures ranging

Fig. 1. Variation of thermodynamic functions with absolute temperature for *trans*-acrylyl chloride.

NOTES

from 100 to 1500 K by treating the molecule as a rigid rotor harmonic oscillator. The thermodynamic functions rise more rapidly in the low temperature range. The trend of variation of thermodynamic functions with temperature is similar to that reported in literature¹¹⁻¹³.

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to Prof. H. L. Bhatnagar, (Retired), Department of Chemistry and Dr. R. M. P. Jaiswal, Department of Physics of Kurukshetra University, for their valuable suggestions and criticism.

References

1. J. E. KATON and FEAIRHELLER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1966, 45, 750.
2. J. E. KATON and FEAIRHELLER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1967, 47, 1248.
3. R. L. REDINGTON, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1975, 62, 4927.
4. S. BHADUR and R. M. P. JAISWAL, *Indian J. Pure Appl. Phys.*, 1982, 20, 421.
5. M. BORN and J. R. OPPENHEIMER, *Ann. Phys.*, 1927, 84, 457.
6. N. B. COLTHUP, L. H. DALY and S. E. WIBERLEY, "Introduction to Infrared and Raman Spectroscopy", New York, 1964.
7. ICSU Committee on Data for Science and Technology, CODATA Bull. No. 11, 1973.
8. W. D. FATELY, R. K. HARRIS, F. A. MILLER and WITKOWSKI, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1965, 21, 231.
9. Y. ANJANEYULU, K. LAL and H. L. BHATNAGAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, 65, 400.
10. K. S. PITZER and W. D. GWINN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1942, 10, 42.
11. C. L. CHATTERJEE, P. P. GARG and R. M. P. JAISWAL, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1978, 34, 943.
12. R. PRASAD and O. P. VERMANI, *Indian J. Phys., Sect. B*, 1982, 56, 170.
13. N. S. RAJMUHON, K. LAL and H. L. BHATNAGAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, 63, 930.